

Image Classification Using CNN Model Based on Deep Learning

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ABSTRACT

In this work, we will use a convolutional neural network to classify images. In the field of visual image analysis, CNNs (a subset of deep neural networks) are the norm. Multilayer perceptron is used to develop CNN; it is based on a hierarchical model that works on network construction and then delivers to a fully linked layer. All the neurons are linked together and their output is processed in this layer. Here, we demonstrate how our system can get the job done in challenging domains like computer vision by using a deep learning approach. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are a machine learning method employed by our system for automated picture categorization. For grayscale picture categorization, our method compares to the Digit of MNIST data set. More processing power is needed for picture classification because of the grayscale images in the training data set. Our model's great accuracy in picture classification can be seen in the experimental phase, where we trained it using a convolutional neural network and obtained a result of 98% accuracy..

Keywords: Image Classification, CNN, Deep Learning

1. INTRODUCTION

With the proliferation of data across several industries, including e-commerce, automotive, healthcare, and gaming, picture categorization has emerged as a hot topic among digital innovators. Facebook is the most glaring use of this technology. With only a few tags, Facebook can accurately recognize your face in photos and place them in the appropriate album. What is the Working of Image Recognition and How it is Used (2017) claims that the technology is almost as good as humans at classifying and recognizing images. Deep learning is one of the most used methods for this technology. When it comes to mimicking human behavior or thought processes, deep learning is classified as Artificial Intelligence. In order to speed up the 'training' process, the system is often pre-populated with hundreds, if not thousands, of input data points. At first, 'training' is provided using all of the input data (Faux & Luthon, 2012). Machine learning is one of the most common systems used for this purpose. Machine learning has come a long way, but there is always room for development. That's why we're going to have to use a deep learning system to do the categorization of images. When it comes to image classification, machine vision operates in a unique setting. This technology can identify recognizable subjects in photographs as well as locations, actions, and text. Image categorization may be performed very well when AI programs are combined with machine vision technology (Haughn M, 2017). Classifying photos into distinct categories based on the content is the primary goal of image classification (Xie, Hong, Zhang, & Tian, 2015). Humans have no trouble categorizing things, while robots have a lot of trouble. Instead of detecting an item as it should be categorized, it consists of unidentifiable patterns. The many ways in which image categorization technology has found use, including in navigation systems for vehicles and robots and in remote sensing. Difficult work is still being done to enhance it, but funding is tight (Xie et al., 2015). Machine vision has a long history with image categorization, and it has recently become a prominent difficulty in the field. There is a large variation within each class of photographs due to factors such as hue, saturation, contrast, and orientation. In order to train a neural network, a large amount of labeled training pictures is needed, and preparing this large amount of data is time-consuming and expensive. (X. Li & Guo, 2013).

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

1. Mamoun Awad, et.al: A Framework for image classification.

In this study, we propose a system for gradually annotating photos in the repository in response to community input. At first, people manually annotate certain photographs to serve as ground truth. This information will be used to train the classifier. Annotation for novel photos not included in the ground truth is predicted by the classifier. The classifier is retrained once user feedback is gathered and used to expand the training set. The system actively solicits user input and retrains the classifier based on the updated data. Semi-automatic picture annotation is made possible by our suggested architecture.

2. Suraj Srinivas, Ravi K. Sarvadeva bhatla, et.al: Introduction to Deep Convolutional Neural Nets for Computer Vision

The success of previous designs for resolving computer vision issues has been dependent to a large extent on these manually built characteristics. Recent advances in deep learning, however, have presented an attractive alternative: the automated acquisition of characteristics uniquely suited to a given task. As a result of this shift in thinking, all computer vision issues are being reexamined through the lens of deep learning. As a result, it's crucial to learn about the specific deep networks that exist.

3. J. Yang, Y.-G.Jiang, A.G. Hauptmann, C.-W. Ngo: Assessing bag-of-visual-words representations in scene classification

An picture may be characterized as a "bag of visual words" using keypoints extracted as prominent image patches, and this representation has been put to use in scene categorization. Classification success relies heavily on the dimension, selection, and weighting of visual words in this representation, although these factors have not been adequately examined in prior work. We apply text categorization techniques such as term weighting, stop word removal, and feature selection to generate image representations that vary in dimension, selection, and weighting of visual words because of the similarity between this representation and the bag-of-words representation of text documents. Extensive research on the TRECVID and PASCAL collection investigate the effect of different representation options on scene categorization. With the data presented here, it should be possible to create visual-word representations with better than average categorization performance.

4. Nadia Jmour, SehlaZayen, AfefAbdelkrim: Convolutional Neural Networks for Image Classification

In this study, we provide a method for traffic sign categorization based on training convolutional neural networks (CNN). In addition, it shows some early results from using this CNN to train features and categorize RGB-D pictures as part of a classification challenge. We investigate the "fine tuning technique" of transfer learning, which entails reusing layers learned on the ImageNet dataset to find a solution for a four-class classification job on a fresh collection of data, as a means of determining the suitable architecture.

5. An TienVo, Hai Son Tran, Thai Hoang Le: Advertisement Image Classification using Convolutional Neural Network

Applications in computer vision where picture categorization is essential include facial expression analysis, satellite imagery analysis, and image-based plant (fruit, flower, leaf) analysis. This research puts out a technique for classifying images that may be used to spot internet ads. The proposed model makes use of a Convolutional Neural Network, which has two parameters (n, m): the number of layers in the network and the number of filters in the Conv layer, respectively. The nLmF-CNN model is suggested. Experiments are used to determine the optimal values of the two parameters (n, m) for ad image categorization. The suggested model uses photos collected online as input data. The nLmF-CNN processing components are built as deep neural networks with the help of the ConvNetJs package. Proposed model results are YES/NO. If the answer is "yes," then the ads will be legible. If the answer is "NO," then the ads are either not showing up or are unclear. Our normalizing dataset testing results (86%) confirmed the viability of the suggested nLmF-CNN model.

3. OBJECTIVES

3.1 EXISTING SYSTEM

Since there are so few methods for processing and classifying photos, doing research in this area is difficult. Classifying pictures according to a set of predetermined criteria is known as image classification. Several studies attempted to address the limitations of image categorization, but all of them yielded only rudimentary illustrations at best. Convolutional neural networks, deep belief networks, support vector machines (SVMs), random forests (RFs), and many other deep neural network approaches are utilized for image categorization. The Biological Neural Network is the inspiration for Artificial Neural Networks (ANN)[26]. Its core concept originates in the field of cognitive science [13], whereby complex actions are achieved via the interconnection of numerous relatively simple computational units. However, it is introduced CNN because of its lack of processing capacity. CNN is often used for image analysis.

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM

- Deep Learning is a subfield of Machine Learning that was developed to bring the field closer to its ultimate aim of mimicking human intelligence.
- Fundamental Ideas Behind Deep Neural Networks
- The depth of a neural network is what sets deep-learning networks apart from the more conventional single-hidden-layer models.
- "Deep" learning is defined as having more than three layers (including input and output).
- Each layer of nodes in a deep-learning network trains on a different subset of characteristics informed by the output of the preceding layer.
- As you go further into a neural network, the nodes' ability to detect characteristics increases as they recombine and aggregate information from earlier layers.

Different DL Models:

- Deep Neural Network
- Deep Boltzmann Machine
- Restricted Boltzmann Machine
- Deep Belief Networks
- Deep Autoencoders
- Recurrent Neural Networks
- Convolutional Neural Networks

In the proposed system, image classification performed by using CNN. The Convolutional layers of a CNN's hidden layers are what make it so good at analyzing images. There are three primary varieties of CNN layer:

- Convolutional layer
- Pooling layer
- Fully connected layer

Depending on the picture's size and resolution, the computer interprets the image as an array of pixel values. Let's pretend we have a jpg picture that's 480 pixels wide and tall. Next, a $480 \times 480 \times 3$ picture is created, with the corresponding RGB values represented by the. Pixels are assigned values between 0 and 255 to indicate their relative brightness [15]. In addition, the picture categorization is fed a numerical array.

4.1. ARCHITECTURE

Fig 1: System Architecture

- **Input Image:** Select input image from any classification such as Animal or fruit or veg
- **Pre-processing** – Converts color image into gray color
- **CNN Model and SVM** : Using this model the object classifies into corresponding categories.

4.2. SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

4.2.1 HARDWARE REQUIREMENTS

Processor	:	Intel Core I3 and above
Processor Speed	:	1.0GHZ or above
RAM	:	4 GB RAM or above
Hard Disk	:	500 GB hard disk or above

4.2.2 SOFTWARE REQUIREMENTS:

Operating System	:	Windows 7/10 or above
Front End	:	Python
Back End	:	SQLite3

4.3 FEASIBILITY STUDY

Preliminary research looks at whether or not the project is doable and whether or not the system will be valuable to the business. The primary goal of the feasibility study is to examine the Technical, Operational, and Economic viability of implementing the proposed changes and debugging the existing, operational system. If there had limitless time and materials, any system would be doable. Management is the focus of the feasibility study. A feasibility study is conducted to determine the viability of an information system project and to provide viable alternatives.

The preliminary inquiry includes a feasibility study, which covers some:

- ✓ Technical Feasibility
- ✓ Operational Feasibility
- ✓ Economical Feasibility

Operational Feasibility

It alludes to how likely it is that the product will really work. Some goods may function perfectly in the lab but fall short when put to the test in the real world. Examining the need for, and the availability of, more technical personnel is part of this process. It entails making assumptions about the system's potential uptake based on the skillsets of the people currently working on the project. It's a tally of how effectively a proposed system addresses issues and makes the most of possibilities discovered in scope definition, as well as how well it meets needs discovered in analysis. It takes a look at whether or not the company is willing to back the new system. The level of management support for the proposed project is a key consideration in making this determination.

Technical Feasibility

This question asks whether the current application is fully supported by commercially-available software. It analyzes the benefits and drawbacks of employing a certain piece of software in development and whether or not doing so is even possible. It also investigates the supplementary instruction required of the workforce for the application to succeed. Next, the organization's technical capacity is measured against the technical needs. If the organization's current level of technical expertise is enough to meet the needs of the systems project, then it is regarded technically viable. The analyst is tasked with determining whether the requested enhancements or additions can be made to the existing technological resources.

Economic Feasibility

It is the ratio of the whole amount spent on producing the product to the total amount received as a result of using the product. If the new system would function in much the same way as the old one, then it would be impractical to create it. Cost-benefit analysis is another name for economic analysis. The efficacy of a new system is often measured using this technique. Economic analysis involves calculating the predicted savings and advantages of a potential system and comparing them with the associated expenses. If the advantages are greater than the disadvantages, the system will be developed and put into operation. Before taking any kind of action, a business owner has to carefully consider the costs and advantages.

4.4 SYSTEM TESTING

Introduction:

The software testing process is the last check on the specifications, designs, and codes that make up a piece of software. The goal of testing is to detect bugs in a software by running it. The goal of testing is to establish whether or not a program is functioning as intended by running it alongside a collection of test cases and analyzing the results.

4.5 TESTING OBJECTIVES:

- Testing is the process of running a software to identify bugs.
- An effective test case design is one that is likely to unearth a previously unknown bug.
- A successful test is one that reveals a previously unknown flaw.

These aforementioned goals need a radical shift in perspective. Software flaws can only be shown by testing, not their absence.

Below mentioned are Testing methodologies:

Unit Testing:

Unit testing's primary objective is to guarantee the integrity of a particular program section.. This test makes sure each component works as intended before moving on to the next. This is why we call it "unit testing," since we test each module separately.

Integration Testing:

It's a methodical approach to building independent software components into a unified whole. Errors that occurred throughout the module are uncovered and verified by this test.

Output Testing:

The purpose of output testing is to determine the accuracy of a particular output.

Validation Testing:

The program is complete and meets all requirements once it has undergone integration testing. However, it must be verified in accordance with the specification in order to discover the unforeseen future mistakes and enhance its dependability.

Approaches to Software Testing:A software developer may use a software testing plan as a guide. The actions involved in testing may be organized ahead of time and carried out in a methodical fashion. This is why it's important to develop a software testing framework, consisting of a series of phases into which we can slot various approaches to designing tests for software. The following traits should be included in every software testing approach:

The complete computer-based system is tested, starting with each individual module and progressing "outward" to their integration.

- Various methods of testing may be useful at various stages.
- Testing is done by both the software's creator and an outside organization.
- Testing and debugging are distinct processes, but testing plans must include room for debugging.

5. DESIGN & ANALYSIS

5.1 FUNCTIONAL DESCRIPTION OF EACH MODULE

Adaptively and automatically learning spatial hierarchies of features, from low- to high-level patterns, CNNs are a sort of deep learning model for processing data with a grid pattern, such as photographs [13, 14].

Multiple layers of a CNN may be trained to recognize various aspects of a picture. Each picture has a filter or kernel applied to it, and the results improve and become more detailed as you go through the layers. Simple characteristics might serve as a starting point for the filters in the lower levels.

5.2 CNN ALGORITHM FOR IMAGE CLASSIFICATION

Step 1: Choose a Dataset

Choose a dataset of your interest or you can also create your own image dataset for solving your own image classification problem.

Step 2: Prepare Dataset for Training

Preparing our dataset for training will involve assigning paths and creating categories(labels), resizing our images.

Resizing images into 200 X 200

Step 3: Create Training Data

Training is an array that will contain image pixel values and the index at which the image in the CATEGORIES list.

Step 4: Shuffle the Dataset

Step 5: Assigning Labels and Features

This shape of both the lists will be used in Classification using the NEURAL NETWORKS.

Step 6: Normalizing X and converting labels to categorical data

Step 7: Split X and Y for use in CNN

Step 8: Define, compile and train the CNN Model

Step 9: Accuracy and Score of model.

5.3. DATAFLOW

Introduction:

In order to solve the issue described in the requirements papers, the design phase is carried out. The transition from the issue domain to the solution domain begins at this stage. In other words, design leads us toward how to describe the demands once we start with what is required.

UML Diagrams:

By adhering to a standard set of syntactic, semantic, and pragmatic norms, the software engineer may express an analytical model in the unified modeling language.

Data Flow Diagram (DFD):

A data flow diagram (DFD) is a graphical depiction of how data moves through a system, including its entry and exit points and its storage locations. Any operational process in a company may be represented effectively with the help of a data flow diagram.

Advantages of DFD:

Users and system administrators alike will have no trouble deciphering these notations. DFD research may be improved by incorporating user input. Inspecting charts and beginning to take precautions early on helps reduce the likelihood of a failed system.

The goal of the "bubble Chart" representation of a DFD is to define the system's requirements and to identify the main changes that will become the design's programs. Therefore, this is the stage at which we begin designing in the most minimal of details. The data flows of a system are represented as a sequence of bubbles in a data flow diagram (DFD).

Notations used to draw DFD are as follows:

Name	Symbol	Meaning
process		Transforms of incoming data flows(s) to outgoing data flows(s).
Data Store		A repository of data that is to be store for use by one or more processes.
Data Flow		Movement of the data in the system.
External Entity		Sources and Destination outside the specified system boundary.

Table:1 Symbols used in DFD

Fig:2 Data Flow Diagram

6. IMPLEMENTATION & RESULT ANALYSIS

Fig3: Main

Fig4: Menu

Fig 5: Read Image

Fig 6: Preprocessing

Fig 7: Classification & Prediction

The Model is trained well with the given images
 The predicted Data is: [2 0 0 0 2]
 The actual data is: [2 0 2 1 0 3]
 The model is 50.0% accurate
 Veg = 17.545939624253084%
 The predicted image is: Veg

Fig 8: Final Output

The Model is trained well with the given images
 The predicted Data is: [2 0 0 0 2]
 The actual data is: [2 0 2 1 0 3]
 The model is 50.0% accurate
 The predicted image is: Animals

7. CONCLUSION

We need a system that can effectively extract features from images and then categorize those features on its own in order to do image classification. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), which comprise Conv-layers to extract features and max pooling to lower the size of an image, were the kind of neural networks that we employed for image classification. This resulted in an accurate categorization of the picture.

The results of the trials demonstrate that the deep learning algorithm is successful since it accurately classifies the photos, even for the parts of the test images that are included in the studies.

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